

**INTERPRETATION OF THE PSYCHOLOGY OF UZBEKISTAN
WOMEN IN MODERN UZBEKISTAN LITERATURE
(On the example of Halima Khudoyberdieva's work)**

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The People's Poet of Uzbekistan Halima Khudoyberdieva is one of the poets who has taken her place in modern Uzbek poetry. She was a mature poet who glorified sincere human feelings and qualities in Uzbek poetry - love and loyalty, kindness and compassion, and in essence, the poet entered literature as a singer of the dreams and aspirations of Uzbek women and girls.

Starting from her first poetry collections, the poetess sought to reveal the magical aspects of the images of women and mothers in her work, to teach that they are not only full-fledged and active members of society, but also its beauty and decoration. The image of a woman has become the main model of the poetess's work.

*Sen daryosan, o'pganini qirg'oq yashirar,
Juftim bo'l deb, chopganini har toq yashirar,
Jannatim, deb quvonmasdan qumloq yashirar,
Sen baribir muqaddassan,
Muqaddas ayol!*

In her interpretation, a woman is the future of any nation and country - a miraculous force that produces healthy and harmonious youth! From this perspective, Halima Khudoyberdieva vividly depicted the thoughts, fantasies, and inner experiences of Uzbek women, striving to instill in her contemporaries a sense of respect and love for women.

*Ayol o'tib borar, sho'x yurib,
Shamollarda soch yoygan ayol.
Ich-ichidan yo'lbars o'kirib,
Sirtidan mayin jilmaygan ayol.*

People's poet of Uzbekistan Halima Khudoyberdieva (1947 - 2018) was born in Boyovut district. Her mother passed away when the future poet was two years old, and her aunt Karshigul Khannazar kizi raised her. Halima Khudoyberdieva came to the attention of the head of Uzbekistan Sharof Rashidov, who came to Syrdarya during her school years. According to the poetess, "After Sharof Rashidov read my poems in the newspaper "Syrdaryo Haqiqati", he called the then regional governor Nasir Mahmudov and the editor-in-chief of the newspaper Ismail Sulaymonov and said, "We need to pay attention to this girl, she needs to go to study, talk to her parents." After that, I remember Nasir Mahmudov and Ismail Sulaymonov coming to our house and talking to my father. And with that, I came to study, to Tashkent. Otherwise, at that time, they would not send girls to study, from our side. In Tashkent, I received a lot of kindness from my dear teachers, Mirtemir aka, dear Zulfiya opa, and Komil Yashin, literary figures who became the pride of our nation. I learned lessons in work and life. Thank God, I was given the happiness of studying with such teachers.

Halima Khudoyberdieva graduated from the Faculty of Journalism of Tashkent State University (now the National University of Uzbekistan) in 1972. She studied at the Higher Literature Course of the Gorky Institute of World Literature in Moscow. According to the poetess, "The two years spent in Moscow cannot be replaced by any other. Moscow gave me a lot. I can say that I entered world literature there. The spirit of my poems written at that time is also different." In Moscow, the poet's poetry collections "Pride" and "White Apples" were translated into Russian. Later, a book of poetry translations entitled "Reshimost" was published.

Ko‘rdim qishloq, go‘zal shaharlar ko‘rdim,

Ohorlari ketib borar, bilmaslar.

Jamalaksoch pari – paykarlar ko‘rdim,

Bahorlari ketib borar bilmaslar.

H. Khudoyberdieva worked as a literary employee, department head, and editor-in-chief of the magazine “Saodat”, department head of the publishing house “Yoshlar”, chairman of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, leading editor of the publishing house “Yozuvchi”, deputy editor-in-chief of the magazine “Sanam”, and department editor of the newspaper “XXI century”.

Halima Khudoyberdieva's first poems were published in 1964, during her school years, in the Yangier district newspaper. After that, his poetry books "First Love" (1968), "White Apples" (1973), "Chaman" (1974), "My Mountains of Support" (1976), "Grandfather Sun" (1977), "Issiqqor" (1979), "Loyalty" (1983), "Mukaddas Ayol" (1987), "There Are Those Who Have Reached These Days", "The Fire of Freedom" (1993), "Tomaris's Sayings" (1996), "I'm on the Road" (2005) and other books were published.

Siz kutasiz. Menam boraman,

Uchib boradurman xuddi o‘q.

Faqat...oldin xat yuboraman,

O‘sha xatni yozganimcha yo‘q...

Qirq yil o‘tdi men tez boraman,

Ranjimangiz, guvoh yeru ko‘k.

Faqat...oldin xat yuboraman,

Xatni hali yozolganim yo‘q.

The poetess's poems have been translated into many foreign languages. The play "Alla" by Tofon Minnullin was staged at the Uzbek National Academic Theater in an authorized translation by Halima Khudoyberdieva. Halima Khudoyberdieva, laureate of the State Prize of Uzbekistan named after Hamza, has

translated works by Fazu Alieva, Silva Kaputikyan, and Ibrohim Yusupov.

In short, as the hero of Uzbekistan Ibrohim Gafurov wrote, the example of the word poem is a prophecy. In it, life in imagination turns into right, and life in right turns into imagination. And this never stops.

All of Halima Khudoyberdieva's writings are full of prophecies; perhaps each of her works is a prophecy. She lived as she wrote. She raised life to the height of poetry, and poetry to the height of life. She created a balance, that is, harmony, between poetry and life. And she didn't just live, she didn't just write: she said it herself: she said it as if she had not drawn a sword: her poems were memorized by her fans. "Not only did they memorize them, they sang and hummed these masterpieces of poetry. Her poems conquered the hearts of the reader. However, it is true that the poetess Halima Khudoyberdieva created a high peak in modern Uzbek literature with her work.

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